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Terms and abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DM	Dissemination Manager
EC	European Commission
EM	Exploitation Manager
GA	Grant Agreement
GAM	General Assembly Meeting
PM	Project Manager
PU	Public
QA	Quality Assurance
RE	Restricted
SC	Steering Committee
TM	Technical Manager
WP	Work package
WPL	Work package Leader

Executive Summary

This document provides technical information on the PLATOON open-source metadata broker (AKA open-source broker, IDS broker), deliverable D3.3. In PLATOON, the core component of Marketplace is the IDS broker (i.e., open-source broker). The broker in the Marketplace would be capable of handling metadata of connectors, resources, and an extension of this broker will also handle the metadata of data apps. The deliverable D3.3 describes the concept of the open-source broker, which facilitates storing and processing the metadata of connectors and resources. The extension of the broker handling metadata of Data Apps(metadata registry) will be reported in the deliverable D3.5, “Marketplace Demonstrator and Report”.

1 What is the Open-source Broker?

The Open-source Broker is a metadata registry for datasets and connectors derived from the International Data Spaces (IDS) Metadata Broker. In contrast to the general IDS Metadata Broker, the Broker Open-source has been tailored to keep the main functionalities of metadata handling for connectors and data resources and querying for the metadata. The open-source broker is one of the main components in the PLATOON Marketplace. As shown in Figure 1, data consumers and data providers with an IDS connector can register their resources in the open-source broker. The broker can be used to register, update, or unregister the connector or resource metadata. Note that the broker does not serve the datasets themselves: querying is performed on metadata only. In PLATOON architecture, as shown in Figure 2, the open-source broker is referring to the functionalities of the Data Source Catalog blob on the Marketplace. It should be clarified here that in Figure 2, the open-source broker and context broker are two completely different components.

Figure 1 Platoon Marketplace Architecture

This document aims to provide assistance for developers to understand the structure and the functions of the Open-source Broker and for IT administrators to know the deployment of the Open-source Broker.

Figure 2 Platoon Architecture

2 Open-source Broker Functions

In Platoon architecture plan, the Open-source Broker will be the main component of Metadata Registry, which is a central component for pilots to register, update or unregister their connector or resource metadata. Pilots can also request the description of the Open-source Broker and also query for any information provided in it.

The following list shows the main functions of the Open-source Broker:

- Description Request:
 - o Description Request is to get the self-description of the Open-source Broker.
- Register/Update Connector:
 - o Register/Update Connector is to register the connector if it doesn't exist in the Open-source Broker or update the connector if it exists in the Open-source Broker.
- Unregister Connector:
 - o Unregister Connector is to unregister the connector from the Open-source Broker.
- Update Resource:
 - o Update Resource is to update the information of a certain resource of a connector.
- Unregister Resource:
 - o Unregister Resource is to remove a certain resource from a connector.

- Query:
 - o Query is to query the SQARL triples in Fuseki triple store.

Note that all data in the Open-source Broker is metadata only!

The register, update and unregister of connector and resource mentioned above are related to metadata as well.

Each function matches a specific IDS message type. For example, for the description request for the Open-source Broker, the connector can send a DescriptionRequestMessage.

The following list shows the relations between the functions and IDS messages:

- Description Request for the Open-source Broker:
 - o DescriptionRequestMessage
- Register/Update Connector:
 - o ConnectorUpdateMessage
- Unregister Connector:
 - o ConnectorUnavailableMessage
- Update Resource:
 - o ResourceUpdateMessage
- Unregister Resource: ResourceUnavailableMessage
- Query:
 - o QueryMessage

Message handlers are created in the code to handle the above messages. In the Open-source Broker, there are four message handlers:

- Description Handler:
 - o DescriptionRequestMessage
- Connector Handler:
 - o ConnectorUpdateMessage, ConnectorUnavailableMessage
- Resource Handler:
 - o ResourceUpdateMessage, ResourceUnavailableMessage
- Query Handler:
 - o QueryMessage

All handlers are added in the AppConfig class to make the Open-source Broker enable such functionalities.

For the further development, the first thing to do is to check which IDS messages should be used to achieve the goal. Then we can create corresponding handlers to handle such messages. At last, we add those handlers in the configuration of Open-source Broker.

The Open-source Broker also includes DAPs service that if the security token of a request is not valid, the Open-source Broker will reject it to ensure unauthorized systems cannot access to the information.

All functions are unit tested in test folders of Maven project. The following command can be used to run all tests:

```
mvn test
```

3 Development

The code of the Open-source Broker is hosted in Platoon Git repository <https://github.com/PLATOONProject/open-source-broker>

The development environment of Open-source Broker consists of two main components. The first one is a Fuseki triple store which is the database storing all metadata and the other is the Open-source Broker core component.

Prerequisite:

- Docker (19.03.13)
- Docker Compose (1.24.0)
- Java (11)
- Maven (3.6.3)

3.1 Set Up Development Environment

The first step is to run a Fuseki instance. In path *docker/composefiles/DEBUG*, run the command:

```
docker-compose up
```

Now the Fuseki instance is running on port 3030. (Figure 3)

Figure 3 Fuseki instance

The next step is to run Open-source Broker core. In path *broker-core*, run the command:

```
mvn spring-boot:run
```

Now the Open-source Broker core is running on port 8080 and the self-description is also presented. (Figure 4)

```

localhost:8080
{
  "@context" : {
    "ids" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/core/",
    "idsvc" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/code/"
  },
  "@type" : "ids:Broker",
  "id" : "http://localhost:8080/",
  "ids:title" : {
    "@value" : "IDS Metadata Broker",
    "@language" : "en"
  },
  "ids:mainInquirer" : {
    "@id" : "https://www.iain.fraunhofer.de/"
  },
  "ids:inquirer" : {
    "@id" : "https://www.iain.fraunhofer.de/"
  },
  "ids:inboundModelVersion" : {
    "@value" : "4.0.3"
  },
  "ids:outboundModelVersion" : {
    "@value" : "4.0.2"
  },
  "ids:hasEndpoint" : {
    "@type" : "ids:ConnectorEndpoint",
    "@id" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/autogen/connectorEndpoint/463d6771-43e6-4498-a01c-9f5156d88332",
    "ids:path" : "/infrastructure",
    "ids:accessURL" : {
      "@id" : "http://localhost:8080/infrastructure"
    },
    "ids:endpointInformation" : {
      "@value" : "This endpoint provides IDS Connector and IDS Resource registration and search capabilities of the IDS Metadata Broker.",
      "@language" : "en"
    },
    "ids:endpointDocumentation" : {
      "@value" : "Dieser Endpunkt ermöglicht die Registrierung von und das Suchen nach IDS Connectoren und IDS Ressourcen an IDS Metadata Broker.",
      "@language" : "de"
    }
  },
  "ids:resourceCatalog" : {
    "@type" : "ids:ResourceCatalog",
    "@id" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/autogen/resourceCatalog/e28526c1-bac3-42fa-844c-af1d797bc4f7",
    "ids:offerResource" : {
      "@type" : "ids:DataResource",
      "@id" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/autogen/dataResource/b3e1c676-3771-4b11-b26f-84c495d375ca",
      "ids:representation" : {
        "@type" : "ids:DataRepresentation",
        "@id" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/autogen/dataRepresentation/ebe088b7-5d5b-4c96-a292-a7d195599e46",
        "ids:instance" : {
          "@type" : "ids:ARTifact",
          "@id" : "http://localhost:8080/connectors/"
        }
      }
    }
  },
  "ids:hasDefaultEndpoint" : {
    "@type" : "ids:ConnectorEndpoint",
    "@id" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/autogen/connectorEndpoint/823d4fa6-c116-8c08-b878-df3b4170f87c",
    "ids:path" : "/",
    "ids:accessURL" : {
      "@id" : "http://localhost:8080/"
    }
  }
}

```

Figure 4 Self-Description

3.2 Interacting with the Open-source Broker

The Open-source Broker accepts and sends messages according to the IDS information model. This model uses the Resource Description Framework (RDF) to leverage the power of linked data. As such, all messages are JSON-LD formatted HTTP Multipart messages.

The multipart endpoint of Open-source Broker is “/infrastructure”. If the Open-source Broker is running, an HTTP POST request can be sent to interact with it. The only header should be “Content-Type” and the value should be “multipart/mixed; boundary=msgpart” as shown in Figure 5.

Note that the boundary value can be changed to any value, but it must be the same boundary in the request body.

Figure 5 Header of the Multipart Request

The following use cases will show how to interact with the Open-source Broker and it will cover all main functions of the Open-source Broker. Note that the localhost environment here acts as the IDS connector to interact with the Open-source Broker.

The response should be a DescriptionResponseMessage with the self-description of the Open-source Broker in the payload. (Figure 7)

```

1  --VDPULU3yfnfZ5UM9rv6gL877gENqVGjqP2s
2  Content-Disposition: form-data; name="header"
3  Content-Type: application/ld+json
4  Content-Length: 2276
5
6  {
7    "@context" : {
8      "ids" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/core/",
9      "idsc" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/code/"
10   },
11   "@type" : "ids:DescriptionResponseMessage",
12   "@id" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/autogen/descriptionResponseMessage/611b5dbb-2ec9-4bec-93ca-4857b06ff5bd",
13   "ids:correlationMessage" : {
14     "@id" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/autogen/descriptionRequestMessage/44133851-14e6-44ac-b592-1dc964b36548"
15   },
16   "ids:issued" : {
17     "@value" : "2021-04-28T12:08:59.651+02:00",
18     "@type" : "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTimeStamp"
19   },
20   "ids:issuerConnector" : {
21     "@id" : "http://localhost:8080/"
22   },
23   "ids:senderAgent" : {
24     "@id" : "https://www.iais.fraunhofer.de"
25   },
26   "ids:securityToken" : {
27     "@type" : "ids:DynamicAttributeToken",
28     "@id" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/autogen/dynamicAttributeToken/12f21edc-ed4c-4caf-a1f3-3ad236cad09c",
29     "ids:tokenValue" : "eyJ0eXAiOiJKV1QiLCJraWQiOiJkZWZhdWx0IiwiaWF0IjoiUlMyNTYiFQ
    .eyJzY29wZXMiOiJsaWNRzYzpjRjNFQ090TkV0VE9SXX0FUVFJJQlVURVNFQ0xMI0sInf1ZCI6Imk2M6SURTX0NPTk5FQ1RPUlNfOL
    1TXpRMU5ERXh0ekF4TmPrPSIsImV4cCI6MTYxOTYwNzQ3Mywic2VjdXpdlHlQcn9naWxLIjoiaWNRzYzpjQVNFQ0NPTk5FQ1RPUlNfOL
    6Imh0dHBzOi8vdzNpZC5vcncvaWNRzYS9jb250ZXh0cy9jb250ZXh0Lnpzb25sZCIsInRyYW55cG9yYdENLcnRzU2hhMjU2IjoiaGVhbnRz
    z0j1I0j050j030jA80jNEOKEy0jhCOjcy0j20kJG0ntLeWlkOkNCOjhDOKM30kI20jg10jc50kE40jIz0kE20kNCOjE10kFC0jE30j
    -RJT0nlvafCynAUBjVpcGUd6zk4Lz7eXJmXjnlIsqFQ0CSpFBUcRqWMEHh0NrxI34KzhYnJwLLrFERLSvpCSFq_gkQXEQqbe5Svsw_
    -cRS0hSR_knuvSwAL0bcuEY713FzjtKfBNHaRgaQdmGT0Lomak-p8PYUa2tv0TizymeXpK8HueJD-DmVucTtCLQ",
30     "ids:tokenFormat" : {
31       "@id" : "idsc:JWT"
32     }
33   },
34   "ids:modelVersion" : "4.0.3",
35   "serialization" : "Lang:JSON-LD",
36   "elementType" : "BrokerImpl"
37 }
38  --VDPULU3yfnfZ5UM9rv6gL877gENqVGjqP2s
39  Content-Disposition: form-data; name="payload"
40  Content-Type: application/ld+json
41  Content-Length: 2724
42
43  {
44    "@context" : {
45      "ids" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/core/",
46      "idsc" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/code/"
47   },
48   "@type" : "ids:Broker",
49   "@id" : "http://localhost:8080/",

```

Figure 7 Description Request Response

3.2.3 Unregister Connector

The multipart message header should be ConnectorUnavailableMessage and the payload should be empty. (Figure 10)

```

+ unregister connector
POST localhost:8080/infrastructure
Authorization
Headers (1)
Body
Pre-request Script
Tests
form-data x-www-form-urlencoded raw binary Text
1 --msgpart
2 Content-Type: application/json; charset=utf-8
3 Content-Disposition: form-data; name="header"
4
5 {
6   "@context" : {
7     "ids" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/core/",
8     "idsc" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/code/"
9   }
10  "@type" : "ids:ConnectorUnavailableMessage",
11  "@id" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/autogen/connectorUnavailableMessage/44133851-14e6-44ac-b592-1dc964b36549",
12  "ids:securityToken" : {
13    "@context" : {
14      "ids" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/core/",
15      "idsc" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/code/"
16    },
17    "@type" : "ids:DynamicAttributeToken",
18    "@id" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/autogen/dynamicAttributeToken/aba2b899-45bf-4ce7-b9be-b3edafb19ab2",
19    "ids:tokenValue" : "eyJ0eKAI0L3KVIQLCJrAWQlOLJkZWZhdW8iIiwiaWwiOiwiYWNlIjoiaUJyMyNTYiFiQ
    .eyJzZ29wZXMlOlsiaWRzYzpjRFRFQ89OTkV0VE9SXB0VUF3JQlVURVNFQWxMI18cInF1ZCI6Inlkc2M6SURTX0NPTK5FQ1RPUlNYQg
    pBNUI6TTNWEFSTWc5PSIsInV4cCI6MTYxODc3MTYxMiwic2VjdKJpdhlfQcn9maWkLIjoiaWRzYzpjRFRFQ89OTkV0VE9SXB0VUF3JQ1RURVNF
    HBzOlhvdzNoZC5vcncvawRzYS9Jb256ZXB0cy9Jb256ZXB0Lnprb252c2ZCI6InRyYW52c29ydENlcnRlZ2NNAjU2IjoIMGVlbnRkYzBl
    OjQ30jA80jNE0kEyoJhC0jcyQ2okJG0mtleWlkKkNC0jODkM30kI20jg10jc50kE40j1z0kE20kNC0JE10kFC0JE30jUw0j3G0ki
    ,ahkV5zRHG00p18o1FwJ0G63ehG7UFvZlCgMP(FY9Fje075A0TgyGka1kK1t3Q5JHfoaTn2x38XlaNs_s14n6j7N0n_zBdA0b3f1
    -FJtrhwj65uZbscTQ1SUEXR88ayDECSK01cFw9Kv68FY4Ht6R4tpuJF3o8b86_T0Yf0yjd3g30yX5cBURAjccZbnPwCv99-1RTT1-1
20   "ids:tokenFormat" : {
21     "@id" : "idsc:JWT"
22   }
23 }
24 {
25   "ids:senderAgent" : {
26     "@id" : "http://example.org"
27   }
28   "ids:affectedConnector" : {
29     "@id" : "https://broker.ids.isst.fraunhofer.de/"
30   }
31   "ids:modelVersion" : "4.0.0",
32   "ids:issued" : {
33     "@value" : "2021-03-10T17:33:26.168+01:00",
34     "@type" : "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTimeStamp"
35   }
36   "ids:issuerConnector" : {
37     "@id" : "https://broker.ids.isst.fraunhofer.de/"
38   }
39 }
--msgpart--

```

Figure 10 Unregister Connector Request

The response should be a MessageProcessedNotificationMessage without payload. (Figure13)

```

1  --cxW4Kz1LFNOTALXsV3Y_Rk995xyoz5
2  Content-Disposition: Form-data; name="header"
3  Content-Type: application/ld+json
4  Content-Length: 2307
5
6  {
7    "@context" : {
8      "ids" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/core/",
9      "idsc" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/code/"
10   },
11   "@type" : "ids:MessageProcessedNotificationMessage",
12   "@id" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/autogen/messageProcessedNotificationMessage/7d93ad52-0db8-4b0a-a909-1c45b2384ec0",
13   "ids:correlationMessage" : {
14     "@id" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/autogen/resourceUpdateMessage/74d475b0-b152-4c74-8273-f65a686c5a9c"
15   },
16   "ids:issued" : {
17     "@value" : "2021-04-28T12:15:43.039+02:00",
18     "@type" : "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTimeStamp"
19   },
20   "ids:issuerConnector" : {
21     "@id" : "http://localhost:8080/"
22   },
23   "ids:senderAgent" : {
24     "@id" : "https://www.lais.fraunhofer.de"
25   },
26   "ids:securityToken" : {
27     "@type" : "ids:DynamicAttributeToken",
28     "@id" : "https://w3id.org/idsa/autogen/dynamicAttributeToken/b5f61010-6b7a-4fdc-8063-74d5a6ca786a",
29     "ids:tokenValue" : "eyJ0eXAiOiJKV1QiLCJraWQiOiJkZWZhdWx0IiwiaWxnbG9udGkiOiJlbnRvbnR1bWNTYiYiQ
    .eyJzY29wZXMiOiJ0eXAiOiJKV1QiLCJraWQiOiJkZWZhdWx0IiwiaWxnbG9udGkiOiJlbnRvbnR1bWNTYiYiQ
    pRMU5ERXh0ekF4TmprPSiSImV4cCI6MTYxOTYwNzQ3MjYwZjVjZjVpdHl0cm9maWxLIjoiaWZpcQVNFx0NPTk5FQ1RPU19TRUNVUkLUWV9QI
    HBzOiBvdzNpZC5vcncvaWRzYS9jb250ZXh0cy9jb250ZXh0Lmpzb25sZCIsInRyYW5zcG9ydENLcncrZUhhMjU2IjoiaGVhZG9uZG9kY0UyOjI0Ij
    OjQ3OjA0OjNEOkEyOjY0Ij0jZG9kY0UyOjI0Ij0jZG9kY0UyOjI0Ij0jZG9kY0UyOjI0Ij0jZG9kY0UyOjI0Ij0jZG9kY0UyOjI0Ij0jZG9kY0UyOjI0Ij
    -RJTGnlvaFcyYnAUBjVpcG90d6zK4Lz7eXjMxjmiSqfQOCSpFBuCrqWMEHnH0NrXl34KzHyNjwLLfFERLLSvpCSFq_gkQXEQqbe5Svsw_tczx0qI
    -cR5oHSR_knuv5wAL0bcuEY713FzjtkfBNHaRGaQdmGT0l0mak-p8PYUa2tv0T1zymeXpK8HUEJ0-DmVqcttLQ",
30     "ids:tokenFormat" : {
31       "@id" : "idsc:JWT"
32     }
33   },
34   "ids:modelVersion" : "4.0.3",
35   "Location" : "<http://localhost:8080/connectors/541260824/1487174079/-715517746>"
36 }
37 --cxW4Kz1LFNOTALXsV3Y_Rk995xyoz5--

```

Figure 13 Update Resource Request Response

4 Deployment

In this chapter, we will provide guidance how to deploy the software on a server. We'll create docker images for each Open-source Broker components and run the corresponding docker containers in the same docker-compose environment so that each component can communicate with each other internally.

The Open-source Broker consists of three components:

- broker-core
- broker-fuseki
- broker-reverseproxy

The broker-core component is the main component of the Open-source Broker, which is a Java environment running the Maven package of our code. The broker-core component will take requests from broker-reverseproxy, handle requests using the same handlers we mentioned in Chapter 3, and use APIs that broker-fuseki provides to either read or write in the Fuseki triple store.

The broker-fuseki component is an instance of Fuseki triple store, which hosts all metadata of the Open-source Broker.

The broker-reverseproxy is a NGINX reverse proxy instance, which hosts the certificate to provide security connection to our Open-source Broker. It also acts as the gateway to redirect requests to the broker-core component.

Prerequisite:

- Docker (19.03.13)
- Docker Compose (1.24.0)

4.1 Recommended System Specifications

In this section, we will provide some guidance as to recommendations for the amount of resources that should be available to smoothly operate the Open-source Broker. The actual amount of resources required heavily depends on the load. In case of very little traffic, fewer resources than listed below might be required.

4.1.1 Hardware

2GB of disk space is required for operating the Open-source Broker, though we recommend providing at least 20GB of free disk storage to avoid running out of disk space with increasing number of registered items. We also recommend reserving at least 2GB of RAM.

To provide enough processing power for all Docker containers, we recommend using a 64bit quad core processor or higher.

4.1.2 Software

We recommend using a Linux based operating system. However, any operating system with a Docker installation can be used (tested on Ubuntu 20.04 and Windows 10). More strict hardware requirements than listed above might apply if a non-Linux operating system is used.

4.1.3 Other

A valid X.509 certificate, signed by a trusted certification authority, is strongly recommended to avoid warnings about insecure HTTPS connections. The certificate needs to be of .crt format and must have the name server.crt. In case your certificate is of .pem format, it can be converted with the following commands, which require OpenSSL to be installed:

```
openssl x509 -in mycert.pem -out server.crt
openssl rsa -in mycert.pem -out server.key
mkdir cert
mv server.crt cert/
mv server.key cert/
```

4.2 Configuring the docker-compose File

The docker-compose file is located in path *docker/composefiles/broker-localhost*.

The most crucial part of adapting the configuration is to provide the correct location of the X.509 certificate in the broker-reverseproxy service. Assuming the location of the certificate is *"/home/ids/cert"*, the corresponding configuration is:

```
services:
  broker-reverseproxy:
    image: registry.gitlab.cc-asp.fraunhofer.de:4567/eis-ids/broker-open/reverseproxy
    volumes:
      - /home/ids/cert:/etc/cert/
    [...]
```

4.3 Downloading the Docker Images

All of the Open-source Broker docker images are currently hosted at the GitLab of Fraunhofer IAIS. No credentials needed to download the images. The following command is for pulling all docker images (in path *docker/composefiles/broker-localhost*):

```
docker-compose pull
```

Note that the docker images will be hosted in a Platoon image registry in the future and how to download the image may change afterwards.

4.4 Starting up the Open-source Broker

To start up the Open-source Broker, run the following command inside the directory of the `docker-compose.yml` file (in path `docker/composefiles/broker-localhost`):

```
docker-compose up -d
```

This process can take several minutes to complete. You can test whether the broker has successfully started by opening <https://localhost>. The result should be a JSON document, providing some general metadata about the Open-source Broker, which should be the same as Figure 2.

4.5 Updating the Open-source Broker

To update an existing installation of the Open-Source Broker, first repeat the steps explained in section “Downloading the Docker Containers”. Containers can be either hot updated or restarted to apply the changes. To hot update a container, run the following command:

```
docker-compose up -d --no-deps --build <container name>
```

Alternatively, one can restart the entire service by running:

```
docker-compose down
```

```
docker-compose up -d
```

5 Conclusion

This deliverable describes how the open-source broker handles the messages sent from the Connectors and stores the metadata of the Connectors in the RDF triple store. Once the Connector (data provider) is registered with the open-source broker, the other Connectors (data consumers) can query the metadata. The deliverable presents the functions that the Open-source Broker supports and provides detailed description for setting up, deploying and interacting with the Open-source Broker in the developing environment. This open-source broker will be extended to handle metadata from Data Apps in M24 and will be reported in deliverable D3.5, “Marketplace Demonstrator and Report”.